

USING THE POTENTIAL OF CREATIVE THINKING IN THE ESL CLASSROOM

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Abstract: To incorporate creative thinking into the process of learning English, teachers must depart from the conventional form of instruction that emphasizes correct and incorrect answers, and be open to relinquishing some authority in order to adopt a more student-centered approach. Teachers can enhance creative thinking in the ESL classroom by implementing various strategies and cultivating an environment conducive to the integration of creative thinking into their lessons.

Key words: creativity, creative thinking, collaboration, ESL classroom, teaching activities
Frequently, students are required to provide answers to questions that are either accurate or incorrect. Alternatively, educators can employ open-ended questions that promote self-reliant cognition and knowledge acquisition. Facilitate the natural progression of talks and the organic development of the lesson wherever possible. This will facilitate the development of a feeling of possession and accountability among your students towards their learning process. Encourage profound contemplation with these queries. Promote students' critical thinking by urging them to delve into the subject matter and reach their own conclusions, rather than providing them with a singular, uncomplicated response. Here are a few instances you might utilize:

Could you summarize our previous lesson using your own phrasing?

If given the opportunity to engage in a dialogue with any someone from the past, whom would you choose to converse with and what specific subject matter would you discuss?

You observe that your student is encountering difficulties in grasping a language idea. What would be your strategy for engaging with them and providing assistance?

Implementing collaborative learning in the classroom is a highly effective strategy for fostering an environment conducive to creative thinking. Engaging in collaborative activities such as think/pair/share, peer review, and group problem-solving can be highly beneficial. These exercises necessitate students to exchange their knowledge, juxtapose their notes, and engage in a collaborative exchange of ideas. When established properly, collaborative activities offer a platform for autonomous cognition while also presenting chances to creatively resolve challenges. Whenever feasible, facilitate students in resolving conflicts by encouraging them to express their grievances verbally. Critical thinking is the fundamental basis for any problem-solving.

Inquisitiveness and a feeling of awe frequently serve as the foundation for innovative thought. To foster curiosity and inquiry, opt for captivating and stimulating activities that instill a desire for further knowledge in your kids.

To foster an inclusive learning environment in ESL programs, it is crucial to establish a foundation of mutual respect that allows for the safe exploration and resolution of cultural differences through dialogue. When students are able to freely articulate their viewpoints without apprehension of retribution from the instructor or their classmates, cultural variety can serve as a potent catalyst for stimulating innovative thought. Students will generate diverse solutions or reactions based on their individual backgrounds and draw inspiration from one another's ideas.

If you aim to foster your pupils' creative thinking, it is important to take into account the individual interests of the learners. Students' motivation to think creatively about a topic will

significantly increase if it personally connects with them. Promote students to bring a preferred book, toy, or cultural artifact to present to the class. Participating in a show-and-share event can enhance conversational and public speaking abilities while fostering self-assurance through a more relaxed and flexible attitude. An alternative suggestion entails granting the pupils the opportunity to organize a class celebration, encompassing all aspects from inception to conclusion. Individuals have the autonomy to select which events to commemorate and which activities to incorporate, and they have the opportunity to participate in constructive discussions. The ultimate outcome is an enjoyable and palpable encounter that rewards their diligent efforts.

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